

Modelling fatigue life prediction of additively manufactured Ti-6Al-4V samples using machine learning approach

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Selective laser melting (SLM)

Ti-6Al-4V

Micro-computed tomography (μ CT)

Fatigue life prediction

Machine learning (ML)

ABSTRACT

In this work, a framework based on the machine learning (ML) approach and Spearman's rank correlation analysis is introduced as an effective instrument to solve the influence of defects detected by micro-computed tomography (μ CT) method, and stress amplitude on the fatigue life performance of AM Ti-6Al-4V. Artificial neural network (ANN), random forest regressor (RFR) and support vector regressor (SVR) models are implemented and optimized. The optimization is performed on training set by tuning the hyperparameters and parameters using the leave-one-out cross validation (LOOCV) technique. The results present comparison between predicted and experimental results and validate the proposed framework.

1. Introduction

Selective laser melting (SLM) is categorized as a powder based fusion laser beam (PBF-LB) type of additive manufacturing (AM) technology. AM is a process of bonding materials to make parts from three-dimensional model data [1]. This method of manufacturing interested aerospace and biomedical fields due to their advantages in terms of weight, design, and functionality. Materials, such as cobalt-based, aluminium and titanium alloys have been produced using SLM technique and their mechanical properties have been presented [2,3,4,5]. The effect of build orientation during the AM process on the very-high-cycle fatigue behaviour was examined [6]. Emerging imperfections due to the AM of Ti-6Al-4V are represented mainly by porosity and lack of fusion (LOF) defects [7,8]. LOF defects are typically produced by deficient amount of energy input and gas pores by gas entrapment or unstable keyhole [9,10,11]. Fatigue performance of SLM Ti-6Al-4V specimens exacerbate both types of defects because they represent stress concentrators inducing the crack propagation. Failures are initiated by surface or near surface defects [8,12]. For defect quantification in AM part the non-destructive testing (NDT) is an integral part [13]. However, several challenges including the characterization of the size and shape of internal faults are persistent, e.g., in relation to scanning resolution and

defect detectability [14]. Nevertheless, X-ray micro-computed tomography (μ CT) is well suited for the evaluation of dense titanium parts providing the three-dimensional distribution of internal defects, e.g., in the contour scanning region [15].

Murakami two-variable parameter [16] predicts fatigue life by describing related defects and inclusions to the AM process. In the study by Hu *et al.* [17] parameter X is proposed which helps increase the correlation of fatigue life to the geometric parameters of critical flaw at the crack starting point and to stress amplitude. Fatigue crack growth rate (FCGR) of AM Ti-6Al-4V was developed by Verma *et al.* [18] using extended finite element method (XFEM). However, XFEM requires highly sophisticated instruments and a time expensive method for each set of parameters. The study of Zhou *et al.* [19] presents 3D, finite element modelling of residual stresses induced during the AM process. Evaluated residual stresses are further combined with Basquin-Goodman approach to model the fatigue life. Micropore-propagation-based model of fatigue life analysis of Ti-6Al-4V manufactured by SLM was proposed by Yin and Li [20], where *in-situ* fatigue scanning electron microscope (SEM) observation technology was applied to measure the size of micropore in specimens. Furthermore, multi-scale damage mechanics-FEM for fatigue life prediction of AM structures of Ti-6Al-4V was used [21]. Nevertheless, these methods are very time consuming to

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijfatigue.2022.107483>

Received 31 October 2022; Received in revised form 11 December 2022; Accepted 20 December 2022

Available online 29 December 2022

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describe the complexity of the imperfections of AM. Hence, it is meaningful to develop a novel methodology which will effectively address the current problems.

Machine learning (ML) models represent an effective and capable technique for solving complex problems, such as evaluation of prediction in structural health monitoring [22], classical mechanics of elasticity and inelasticity [23], approximation of partial differential equations in computational mechanics [24], optimization of SLM AM process [25], online quality monitoring of AM process [26], material properties analysis [27], lightweight design [28], modelling fatigue life prediction of bending polymer films using random forest regressor (RFR) [29] and for the modelling very-high-cycle fatigue life prediction of SLM Ti-6Al-4V parts [30]. ML-based models such as K-Nearest Neighbour (KNN) model [31] or faster region-based convolutional neural network (R-CNN) model using a mobile phone [32] was used for prediction of FCGR of AM Ti-6Al-4V. For the modelling fatigue life prediction of SLM Ti-6Al-4V samples, the combination of *post-mortem* synchrotron radiation X-ray micro-computed tomography (SR- μ CT) and the support vector regressor (SVR) model was investigated by Boa *et al.* [33]. The Artificial neural network (ANN), the RFR and the SVR models in combination with continuum damage mechanics (CDM) were used for the prediction of fatigue life of AM steel, titanium and aluminium alloys commonly used in the aerospace engineering [34,35]. Wang *et al.* [36] introduced ML model based on the CDM and sensitive features selected by Pearson correlation coefficient (PCC). To achieve the highest accuracy, the hyperparameters and parameters of ML models are tuned using different types of values and K-fold cross validation technique. A fatigue life prediction using optimized SVR model of hyperparameters (C , ϵ and γ), and 5-fold cross validation method was performed by Boa *et al.* [33]. The variable configuration of ANN and RFR models was used for fatigue life prediction as presented by Zhan and Li [34]. Different numbers of hidden layers and neurons were compared in relation to the ANN model and various quantity of decision trees, sensitive parameters, and maximal depth of the trees were compared for the RFR model.

In this study, the novel framework regarding the pre-processing stage of modelling and optimization of ML models is proposed. The Spearman's rank correlation analysis of features (size, location, shape of defect and stress amplitude) to fatigue life in logarithmic scale is evaluated using experimental results in the pre-process of creating the training and test sets. Based on the correlation analysis only the sensitive features are selected in the final dataset in order to increase the efficiency and accuracy of ML models. All data used for training the ML models are based on the μ CT measurement and fatigue tests performed with stress ratio $R = -1$. For the prediction of fatigue life, the ANN, RFR and SVR models are used. Each model is optimized using the maximal K-fold cross validation method called leave-one-out cross validation (LOOCV). To our best understanding, no studies have investigated and tuned the following parameters for the modelling of fatigue life prediction of AM samples: the optimization of the kernel function of the SVR model, activation function and algorithm used in the ANN model, and further minimal number of splits of internal nodes in decision trees of the RFR model. Furthermore, more detailed optimization of hyperparameters and parameters is performed and accuracy of fatigue life prediction by all ML models is investigated and discussed in this study.

2. Dataset establishment

2.1. Typology of samples

The samples were 3D printed by SLM method at Premet Kft. by Sisma Mysint 100 RM machine with continuous laser beam. Grade 5 Ti-6Al-4V powder was used. The specimens have been printed in longitudinal position without support, the layers are perpendicular to the loading direction (regarding the further fatigue testing). After SLM process the specimens were heat-treated by 600 °C for 1.5 h to reduce residual stresses. Based on the surface finish of samples, three batches were

Fig. 1. Dimensions of a sample (in mm).

created with the total amount of 29 samples. Namely, an as built (AB) batch of 10 samples without any surface finish, then a batch of 10 samples milled by computer numerical control (CNC), and lastly an electropolished (EP) batch of 9 samples. Dimensions of AM Ti-6Al-4V samples is shown in Fig. 1.

Second batch of samples was post-processed by conventional CNC milling technique. The milling was performed using CMX 50 U (DMG Mori) machine with SilverLine D6 R0.25 mm (WNT Performance) tool. Regarding the EP samples, their surface structures were flattened by chemical etching (pickling) and electropolishing with targeted hydrodynamic control of the electrolyte layer and a targeted selection of (environmentally friendly) chemicals. A chloride-based ethanolic electrolyte was used for electropolishing. Prior to electrochemical polishing, the metallic workpieces were cleaned, degreased and acid pickled to remove the oxides and the colours formed by the heating. The pickling process to remove the oxide layers formed during heat treatment was performed using HNO_3 (Bonderite C-1C 4104 Aero). After pickling, an optimized electropolishing process was performed (electrolyte based on AlCl_3 and ZnCl_2 in organic solvents at a potential of 100–150 V).

2.2. Compilation of the dataset

The establishment of the dataset is dependent only on experimental procedures. The overview of the compilation process of the dataset is depicted in Fig. 2.

Before the fatigue tests, all batches of samples (29 samples in total) were analysed by micro-computed tomography (μ CT). For the μ CT measurement, Nanotom 180NF (GE Phoenix, X-ray) micro-focus XCT system was used. The central part of the specimens was scanned resulting in a range of interest (ROI) of 9 mm in height with voxel size of 5 μm . The assigned coordinate system and ROI during the μ CT measurement are shown in Fig. 3.

Acceleration voltage was set to 130 kV, using a current of 130 μA and an exposure time of 800 ms. In total, 1500 projections were acquired per scan. Post-processing was performed in VGSTUDIO MAX 3.5 (Volume Graphics GmbH). From the observed μ CT data, several parameters were analysed for each batch of samples. Parameter d_{size} indicates the diameter of circumscribed sphere of the defect (see Fig. 4a). Furthermore, for individual defect of a sample the d_{loc} is analysed in plane XY. The d_{loc} describes minimal (perpendicular) distance of individual defect from the free surface of a sample (see Fig. 4b). Lastly, the projected area of individual defects in planes YZ, XZ and XY ($d_{\Sigma\text{area, YZ}}$, $d_{\Sigma\text{area, XZ}}$, and $d_{\Sigma\text{area, XY}}$, respectively) is summed. These parameters describe globally the shape of the defect for each sample and are shown by the 3D plot in Fig. 5b. The global shape along X axis (plane YZ) and Y axis (plane XZ) is similar. However, the shape along Z axis (plane XY) is different compared to other directions especially regarding the CNC and EP batches, which means its shape is not spherical.

Distribution of all defects for each batch is shown in Fig. 5a. Furthermore, number of d_{size} ($n_{d_{\text{size}}}$) and of d_{loc} ($n_{d_{\text{loc}}}$) were evaluated and sorted into equal five intervals of 100 μm and 300 μm , in range of (0, 500] μm and (0, 1500] μm , respectively. The variables $n_{d_{\text{size}}}$ and $n_{d_{\text{loc}}}$ are demonstrated by the histogram in Fig. 5c and Fig. 5d, in that order.

The fatigue tests were done under load control using a harmonic loading (sinusoidal shape of the loading cycle) with a constant load

Fig. 2. Schema of the compilation process of the dataset.

Fig. 3. Range of interest (ROI) and example distribution of defects measured by μ CT method in AB sample #9, CNC sample #16 and EP sample #22.

Fig. 4. Definition of defect parameters: (a) diameter of defect, d_{size} ; (b) minimal distance of defect from the free surface of a sample, d_{loc} .

amplitude. Obtained experimental results of uniaxial fatigue tests were done by means of Sinus 100 kN (Instron) load cell testing machine using hydraulic wedge grips. Cyclic loading of the specimens was performed at one level of stress ratio $R = -1$ (tension-compression, symmetric mode) and at nominal test frequency of 10 Hz. The fatigue life (N) and stress amplitude (σ_a) were observed from the performed fatigue tests. The measured values of N (cycle) and σ_a (MPa) are depicted by scatter plot in Fig. 6. In general, the surface treatment such as CNC and EP methods decrease surface roughness which improves fatigue behaviour of SLM Ti-6Al-4V samples [37,38,39]. However, previous statement is not validated by performed fatigue tests because the fatigue life of CNC and EP samples is lower then for AB samples (see Fig. 6). Therefore, in this

study the surface roughness is not further considered in the modelling of fatigue life prediction.

2.3. Z-score normalization of the dataset

In the pre-processing stage of using the ML models the z-score normalization technique is used to eliminate differences in the degree of variability of the original dataset [40]. Z-score normalization is calculated by following formula.

$$x_z = \frac{x - \mu}{\sigma} \tag{1}$$

Fig. 5. Analysed μ CT measurements for all batches of samples: (a) Overall distribution of defects by box and scatter plots; (b) 3D plot of d_{size} , d_{loc} , and $\Sigma_{area, XY}$, $\Sigma_{area, YZ}$, and $\Sigma_{area, XZ}$; (c) histogram of $n_{d_{size}}$ for 5 intervals of 100 μm in range (0, 500] μm ; (d) histogram of $n_{d_{loc}}$ for 5 intervals of 300 μm in range (0, 1500] μm .

where x_z is z-scored value of parameter, x is the original value of parameter, μ and σ are the mean and standard deviation of the original dataset, respectively.

To achieve normal distribution of the observed values of fatigue life (N) from fatigue tests the values were transformed to logarithmic scale ($\log N$), see Fig. 7. For further analysis and comparison with predicted values by ML models the $\log N$ is used.

2.4. Split of the dataset

Three different batches of samples are presented in this work (AB, CNC and EP). Based on the workflow of ML models (see Fig. 11) the z-scored dataset must be split into training and test sets in order to prevent biasing the accuracy of the model. The training (69% of total amount, 20 samples) and test (31% of total amount, 9 samples) sets which were pseudo-randomly selected are listed in the Table 1.

2.5. Spearman's rank correlation analysis

The Spearman's rank correlation coefficient (SRCC) is denoted as r_s . The SRCC is the Pearson correlation coefficient between the rank variables. The calculation of r_s is carried out using the following equation.

$$r_s = \frac{\text{Cov}(X_r, Y_r)}{\text{Std}(X_r)\text{Std}(Y_r)} \quad (2)$$

where $\text{Cov}(\cdot)$ is the covariance, $\text{Std}(\cdot)$ is the standard deviation of rank variables X_r, Y_r . In this study the X_r is represented by input vector of variables (features) and Y_r by output vector (measured fatigue life), see Fig. 7. The Spearman coefficient r_s was determined for the training set. Evaluated values of r_s where the correlation between each variable of input vector and output vector was calculated are recorded in Table 2. The value of $r_s \leq |0.05|$ is deemed as a weak relationship between examined vectors. Due to the accuracy of the ML model, these insensitive variables are not further considered in the training and test sets in the modelling of fatigue life prediction.

Fig. 6. Scatter plot and regressions lines of the experimental results of fatigue life (N) and stress amplitude (σ_a) from the performed fatigue tests for each batch.

Fig. 7. Distribution of fatigue life (N) and fatigue life in logarithmic scale ($\log N$).

Table 1
Training and test sets for the ML models.

Type of set	Type of surface finish (label of samples)		
	AB (#sample 1–10)	CNC (#sample 11–20)	EP (#sample 21–29)
Training	2, 3, 5, 6, 8, 9, 10	11, 12, 14, 15, 17, 18, 20	21, 23, 25, 26, 27, 29
Test	1, 4, 7	13, 16, 19	22, 24, 28

3. Machine learning models

3.1. Artificial neural network model

The structure of the ML algorithm of the ANN model is based on the

Table 2

Spearman’s rank correlation analysis of training set with experimental measured fatigue life ($\log N$).

Variable	r_s (1)	Insensitive
$n_{d_{disc}} \in (0, 100] \mu\text{m}$	0.33	False
$n_{d_{disc}} \in (100, 200] \mu\text{m}$	-0.42	False
$n_{d_{disc}} \in (200, 300] \mu\text{m}$	-0.52	False
$n_{d_{disc}} \in (300, 400] \mu\text{m}$	-0.28	False
$n_{d_{disc}} \in (400, 500] \mu\text{m}$	-0.21	False
$n_{d_{loc}} \in (0, 300] \mu\text{m}$	0.25	False
$n_{d_{loc}} \in (300, 600] \mu\text{m}$	0.08	False
$n_{d_{loc}} \in (600, 900] \mu\text{m}$	-0.09	False
$n_{d_{loc}} \in (900, 1200] \mu\text{m}$	-0.07	False
$n_{d_{loc}} \in (1200, 1500] \mu\text{m}$	-0.08	False
$d_{\sum area, YZ}$	-0.05	True
$d_{\sum area, XZ}$	-0.02	True
$d_{\sum area, XY}$	-0.13	False
σ_a	-0.95	False

functionality of brain neural network [41]. In this article, the multi-layer perceptron (MLP) ANN regressor is used. An ANN model is divided into three layers, namely, input, hidden and output layers. The architecture of the ANN model is shown in Fig. 8.

The number of neurons of input and output layers is equal to the number of variables in both layers. The regression function y_i of i -th neuron could be characterized by the following formula [42].

$$y_i = f_i \left(\sum w_{ij} x_j - t_i \right) \quad (3)$$

where x_j is j -th input feature, w_{ij} are weights, t_i is a threshold parameter, and output regression function y_i is estimated by activation function f_i (such as linear, rectified linear, hyperbolic tangent and sigmoid). The efficiency of the training of the ANN model is based on the back propagation technique and various learning algorithms (such as limited Broyden-Fletcher-Goldfarb-Shanno, an optimizer from the quasi-Newton methods, stochastic gradient-based optimizer, and stochastic gradient descent) which update the weights by each iteration to minimize the error function. The error function is expressed as [43].

$$E = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^n \|y_i - y_i^{true}\|^2 \quad (4)$$

where E is the error function, n is number of samples in dataset, y_i is actual output of the regression function and y_i^{true} is the true value of fatigue life from experimental fatigue testing.

3.2. Random forest regression model

A supervised ML algorithm called Random Forest (RF) belongs to the category of ensemble ML algorithms and is based on the statistical theory [44]. The schema of the RFR algorithm is shown in Fig. 9. Using the bootstrap technique, the original dataset $D_i = \{(X_1, y_1), (X_2, y_2), \dots, (X_i, y_i)\}$ is divided into multiple sub-datasets $S_j = \{(X_1, y_1), (X_2, y_2), \dots, (X_j, y_j)\}$, where $X = [X_{n1}, X_{n2}, \dots, X_{nl}]$ and $y = [y_{n1}, y_{n2}, \dots, y_{nm}]$ are the input and output vectors, respectively. At this stage, training decision trees DT_k , where $k \in \mathbb{N}$, are created. Due to the bootstrap approach, approximately one-third of the samples in each decision tree are the same. The quality of the split of each decision tree is measure by mean squared error (MSE) which is expressed as follows.

$$MSE_{DT_k} = \frac{1}{k} \sum_{p=1}^k (y_p^{true} - y_p^{pre})^2 \quad (5)$$

where y_p^{true} is the true value of fatigue life from experimental fatigue testing, y_p^{pre} is the value predicted by the RFR model and k represents the number of the decision tree. Diversity of the decision trees in the forest is

Fig. 8. Overview of the ANN model.

Fig. 9. Schema of the RFR model.

secured by the randomized selection of input features. In the next step, the output vector of prediction y_k^{pre} for each decision tree DT_k is calculated. Then, the final prediction of RFR ML model is obtained from the following equation [45].

$$y_{RFR} = \frac{1}{k} \sum_{p=1}^k y_p^{pre} = \frac{1}{k} \sum_{p=1}^k f(X, S_j^p) \quad (6)$$

where y_{RFR} is the average of all calculated y_k^{pre} in the previous step. This training process is commonly known as bagging (bootstrap aggregating).

3.3. Support vector regressor model

SVR is derived from the supervised ML algorithm called support vector machines (SVM) which is used for classification problems. The SVR model used in this work solves the regression problem of continuous variable ($\log N$ in this study) and the optimization problem by achieving the minimum of ϵ -insensitive loss function and by obtaining the flattest hyperplane with minimum error [46]. Standard form of SVR model is as follows [47].

$$\min_{w, b, \xi, \xi^*} \left\{ \frac{1}{2} w^T w + C \left(\sum_{i=1}^N (\xi_i + \xi_i^*) \right) \right\}$$

$$s.t. \begin{cases} w^T \phi(x_i) + b - y_i \leq \epsilon + \xi_i \\ y_i - w^T \phi(x_i) - b \leq \epsilon + \xi_i^* \\ \xi_i, \xi_i^* \geq 0 \\ i = 1, 2, \dots, N \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

in which x_i is the input feature vector, y_i is output vector to be estimated by the regression function, w is the weight coefficient, b is the bias term, $\phi(x_i)$ is the non-linear function, C is the penalty coefficient and ϵ represents the maximum acceptable error. The ξ_i and ξ_i^* are relaxation factors. Eq. (7) is transformed by Lagrangian function into the dual optimization problem [48] according to Karush-Kuhn-Tucker conditions [49].

$$\max_{\alpha, \alpha^*} \left\{ \sum_{i=1}^N y_i (\alpha_i^* - \alpha_i) - \epsilon \sum_{i=1}^N (\alpha_i^* + \alpha_i) - \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i,j=1}^N (\alpha_i^* - \alpha_i) (\alpha_j^* - \alpha_j) K(x_i, x_j) \right\}$$

Fig. 10. Diagram of the SVR model.

$$s.t. \begin{cases} \sum_{i=1}^N (\alpha_i^* + \alpha_i) = 0 \\ 0 \leq \alpha_i, \alpha_i^* \leq C \\ i, j = 1, 2, \dots, N \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

where α_i, α_i^* are Lagrangian multipliers and $K(x_i, x_j)$ is the kernel function that satisfies the technical condition called Mercer's theorem [50]. This function has high impact on the capability of the SVR model.

Furthermore, the regression function is expressed as follows [36].

$$f(x) = \sum_{i=1}^N (\alpha_i^* - \alpha_i) K(x_i, x) + y_i + \varepsilon - \sum_{j=1}^N (\alpha_j^* - \alpha_j) K(x_j, x) \quad (9)$$

The overview of the SVR model is shown in Fig. 10.

3.4. Model accuracy criteria

To quantify the accuracy of fatigue life prediction of individual ML models and of further comparison analysis, the coefficient of determination R^2 and mean absolute percentage error $MAPE$ were selected and evaluated. The closer the value of R^2 is to 1, the more accurate the prediction of the ML model is. $MAPE$ is calculated as a mean absolute average percentage error of predicted and measured fatigue life during the fatigue test. The closer the value of $MAPE$ is to 0, the higher the accuracy of the prediction of the ML model. The robustness of $MAPE$ is high because it normalizes the error of each predicted result [36]. The formulas of R^2 and $MAPE$ are described in Eq. (10) and (11), respectively.

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i^{true} - y_i^{pre})^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i^{true} - y_{mean})^2} \quad (10)$$

$$MAPE = \frac{100}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left| \frac{y_i^{true} - y_i^{pre}}{y_i^{true}} \right| \quad (11)$$

where n is the number of evaluated samples, y_i^{true} is the value of fatigue life from experimental fatigue testing, y_i^{pre} is the value predicted by

Fig. 11. Proposed framework of the modelling process of fatigue life prediction.

Table 3
Tuning hyperparameters and parameters of the considered ML models.

ML model	Tuning entity	Type	Range	No. of values
ANN	hyperparameter $h_{1,i}$	numeric	$i \in \{20, 40, 80\}$,	3
	hyperparameter $h_{2,j}$	numeric	$j \in \{0, 10, 20, 40\}$,	4
	hyperparameter $h_{3,k}$	numeric	$k \in \{0, 5, 10, 20\}$	4
	parameter f_l	function	$l \in \{\text{identity, RELU, sigmoid, tanh}\}$	4
	parameter a_m	discrete	$m \in \{\text{ADAM, LBFGS, SGD}\}$	3
RFR	hyperparameter $n_{iter,n}$	numeric	$n \in \{10, 50, 100, 500, 1000, 5000\}$	6
	hyperparameter $n_{DT,p}$	numeric	$p \in \{16, 32, 64, 128\}$	4
	hyperparameter $n_{depth,q}$	numeric	$q \in \{2, 4, 8, 16\}$	4
	hyperparameter $n_{split,r}$	numeric	$r \in \{2, 4, 6, 8\}$.	4
SVR	hyperparameter C	numeric	$[10, 20, \dots, 90, 100]$	10
	hyperparameter ε	numeric	$[10^{-6}, 5 \times 10^{-6}, \dots, 5, 10]$	15
	hyperparameter γ	numeric	$[10^{-6}, 5 \times 10^{-6}, \dots, 5, 10]$	15
	parameter K_t	function	$t \in \{\text{poly, RBF, tanh}\}$	3

the ML model and y_{mean} is the arithmetic average of experimental results.

4. Optimization of machine learning models

4.1. Tuning the hyperparameters and parameters

During the optimization process the best combination of setting the hyperparameters and parameters of the ML model is sought. Parameter is internal to the ML model (e.g., used algorithm), hyperparameter is the explicitly restricted parameter that affects the training process (e.g., number of iterations). Prior to the optimization process, the tuning range of values of hyperparameters and parameters needs to be set. In addition, the dataset is split into the training and test sets (for the split-applied see Table 1). Only the training set are used for tuning the models. The optimization set for each ML model is described in Table 3. The number and range of tuning entities were defined based on the time consumption of the optimization process.

For the ANN model two hyperparameters and two parameters are tuned. The first hyperparameter is the number of hidden layers $h_{1,i}$, $h_{2,j}$ and $h_{3,k}$ where $i \in \{20, 40, 80\}$, $j \in \{0, 10, 20, 40\}$, and $k \in \{0, 5, 10, 20\}$, which means that the maximum of three and minimum of one hidden layer is considered. Model's accuracy is also affected by the activation function (f_i) considered for the hidden layers. The four types of functions were investigated: identity activation function $f_{identity} = x$, rectified linear unit (RELU) function $f_{RELU} = \max(0, x)$, sigmoid function $f_{sigmoid} = \frac{1}{1+e^{-x}}$, and hyperbolic tangent function $f_{tanh} = \tanh(x)$. In addition, three learning algorithms (a_m), stochastic gradient-based optimizer (ADAM), limited Broyden-Fletcher-Goldfarb-Shanno (LBFGS), an optimizer from the quasi-Newton methods, and stochastic gradient descent (SGD) are used. Last tuned hyperparameter for the ANN model is the number of iterations ($n_{iter,n}$), where $n_{iter,n} \in \{10, 50, 100, 500, 1000, 5000\}$. For the RFR model three hyperparameters are tuned. Namely, the number of decision trees $n_{DT,p} \in \{16, 32, 64, 128\}$, maximal depth of the decision tree $n_{depth,q} \in \{2, 4, 8, 16\}$, and the minimum number of samples required to split an internal node $n_{split,r} \in \{2, 4, 6, 8\}$. Furthermore, for the SVR model, the three hyperparameters C , ϵ , γ and the kernel function (K_t) are optimized. These hyperparameters are critical regarding the generalization ability and accuracy of the SVR model. Hyperparameter C acquires 10 various values and hyperparameters ϵ and γ acquire 15 different values. Explicitly, the considered intervals are: $C \in [10, 20, \dots, 90, 100]$, $\epsilon \in [10^{-6}, 5 \times 10^{-6}, \dots, 5, 10]$, and $\gamma \in [10^{-6}, 5 \times 10^{-6}, \dots, 5, 10]$. For the K_t three types of functions are investigated. Firstly, the third degree polynomial function $K_{poly} = -\gamma \langle x_i, x \rangle^3$ secondly, the radial based function (RBF) $K_{RBF} = \exp(-\gamma \|x_i - x\|^2)$ and lastly, the hyperbolic tangent function $K_{tanh} = \tanh \langle x_i, x \rangle$.

4.2. Leave-one-out cross validation

In the optimization loop (see Fig. 11), when the ML model is selected and the configuration is set, the leave-one-out cross validation (LOOCV) is implemented. LOOCV is a cross validation technique in which the dataset is split into K -folds, where for the LOOCV the value of K is equal to the number of samples in training set, in other words LOOCV procedure creates maximum splits of training set. Once split, each subset is gradually used as a validation set while all other subsets together are used as a training set. LOOCV method is commonly used especially when dataset size is considered as small [51]. When the training of the ML model for all considered values of hyperparameters or parameters is done, the model accuracy by MAPE is evaluated for z-scored values. The state when the lowest MAPE is observed is assumed to be an optimized model.

Table 4
Final tuned values of (hyper)parameters of the optimized ML models.

ML model	MAPE (%)	Tuning entity	Value
ANN	0.266	hyperparameter $h_{1,i}$	$h_{1,80}$
		hyperparameter $h_{2,j}$	$h_{2,0}$
		hyperparameter $h_{3,k}$	$h_{3,0}$
		parameter f_i	$f_{sigmoid}$
		parameter a_m	a_{LBFGS}
RFR	0.603	hyperparameter $n_{iter,n}$	$n_{iter,50}$
		hyperparameter $n_{DT,p}$	$n_{DT,64}$
		hyperparameter $n_{depth,q}$	$n_{depth,4}$
		hyperparameter $n_{split,r}$	$n_{split,4}$
SVR	0.350	hyperparameter C	20
		hyperparameter ϵ	0.100
		hyperparameter γ	0.010
		parameter K_t	K_{tanh}

Fig. 12. Optimization of hyperparameter number of iterations ($n_{iter,n}$) of the ANN model.

5. Results and discussion

5.1. Configuration and accuracy of the optimized ML models

Optimized ML models with the best parameters and corresponding model accuracy of prediction by MAPE (evaluated for z-scored values) are recorded in Table 4.

As a demonstration of optimization process the optimizing of hyperparameter number of iterations ($n_{iter,n}$) is shown in Fig. 12. The optimum value of $n_{iter,n} = 50$ when $MAPE = 0.266\%$. The optimization is presented with tuned entities of the ANN model ($h_{1,80}$, $h_{2,0}$, $h_{3,0}$, $f_{sigmoid}$ and a_{LBFGS}), see Table 4.

The highest training accuracy is achieved by the ANN model because the $MAPE = 0.266\%$. Based on the final values of tuning entities, we can conclude that in this study the optimized configuration of hyperparameters for the ANN model are only 1 hidden layer with 80 neurons ($h_{1,80}$) and number of iteration is equal to 50 ($n_{iter,50}$). Regarding the parameters f_i and a_m , the highest accuracy is evaluated using $f_{sigmoid}$ and a_{LBFGS} . The worst performance of optimization process based on the values of MAPE is calculated for the RFR model ($MAPE = 0.603\%$). Final optimized hyperparameters acquired values: $n_{DT,64}$, $n_{depth,4}$ and $n_{split,4}$. Finally, the SVR model's accuracy is 0.350%. Optimized values of the hyperparameters are: $C = 20$, $\epsilon = 0.1$ and $\gamma = 0.01$. Best suited kernel function K_{tanh} was evaluated.

The quality of the replication of the experimental results of training

Fig. 13. Results of calculated fatigue life by all optimized ML models (with tuned hyperparameters and parameters) and its comparison with the experimental results of training set using LOOCV method: (a) level of determination by R^2 ; (b) comparison of absolute values by bar plot.

set of fatigue life $\log N$ by all optimized ML models using LOOCV technique is evaluated by R^2 and shown by double coordinate system in Fig. 13a. The individual prediction of samples is presented using markers. The closer the marker is to the equity line, the more the determination increases. In addition, for the comparison of the absolute values of each training sample, the bar plots are used in Fig. 13b.

The calculated values of R^2 for each ML model are listed in Table 5. Based on the values of R^2 the highest accuracy of prediction of fatigue

Table 5
Comparison of prediction accuracy of the optimized ML models for the training set.

ML model	R^2 (1)
ANN	0.944
RFR	0.822
SVR	0.924

(a)

(b)

Fig. 14. Results of calculated fatigue life by all fitted ML models and its comparison with experimental results for test set: (a) level of determination by R^2 ; (b) comparison of absolute values by bar plot.

life in optimization process is achieved by ANN model with value of $R^2 = 0.944$. On the contrary, slightly worse performance is reached by the RFR model ($R^2 = 0.822$) and the SVR models ($R^2 = 0.924$).

5.2. Fatigue life prediction

The ML models with tuned hyperparameters and parameters are set and fitted to all the training set. Eventually, the fitted ML models (see

overview of framework in Fig. 11) are used for the prediction of fatigue life $\log N$ of test set. The level of determination R^2 of predicted fatigue life $\log N$ by fitted ML models compared to the observed experimental results in the fatigue tests is shown by double coordinate system in Fig. 14a. The individual prediction of samples is depicted by markers. The closer the marker is to the equity line, the higher the accuracy of the prediction. Furthermore, the comparison of the calculated absolute values is shown using bar plots in Fig. 14b.

Table 6

Comparison of prediction accuracy of fitted ML models for the test set.

ML model	R^2 (1)	MAPE (%)
ANN	0.848	2.980
RFR	0.827	3.590
SVR	0.807	3.059

The calculated values of R^2 and *MAPE* (computed for original values) for each ML model are listed in Table 6. Based on the values of R^2 and *MAPE*, the highest accuracy of prediction of fatigue life in testing procedure is achieved by the ANN model with $R^2 = 0.848$ and *MAPE* = 2.980%. On the contrary, slightly worse forecasted performance is calculated using the RFR model ($R^2 = 0.827$, *MAPE* = 3.590%) and SVR model ($R^2 = 0.807$, *MAPE* = 3.059%). Overall, the average accuracy of the ML models is concluded to be high because the value of *MAPE* is not higher than 3.6% in any of the cases.

6. Conclusion

The fatigue life prediction of 3 batches of samples (29 samples totally) of Ti-6Al-4V AM by SLM method was evaluated using the ML approach. The dataset was based on the experimental data from μ CT measurement and fatigue tests. The μ CT measurement described the imperfections induced by AM method for all batches of samples. Manufacturing defects were characterized by the size, location, and shape. By fatigue testing stress amplitude and the corresponding cycles of fatigue life were obtained. ML models are trained on the pseudo-randomly selected 20 samples and then tested on the remaining 9 samples. The Spearman's rank correlation analysis was carried out to exclude insensitive variables and increase the efficiency and accuracy of the ML models. In this study, the ANN, RFR and SVR models are used. To achieve the highest accuracy of prediction of the ML models, the hyperparameters and parameters were tuned using LOOCV technique. The state with the lowest observed *MAPE* was assumed to be the optimized model. When comparing the ANN model, RFR model and SVR model, the highest accuracy of prediction of fatigue life was found to be performed by the ANN model with $R^2 = 0.848$ and *MAPE* = 2.980%. The results show high accuracy of the modelled prediction of fatigue life using the ML approach based on the defect parameters described by μ CT and stress amplitude. To achieve an even higher accuracy of the ML models, the residual stress should be considered in further studies. In addition to that, expansion of the training set, types of AM, used material, stress amplitude levels, a broader lifetime range for fatigue, and different stress ratios should be used to create more comprehensive ML models.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

The data that has been used is confidential.

Acknowledgement

The research leading to this work has received funding from the European Community's H2020 for the Clean Sky joint technology initiative under grant agreement No. 101007830 and from the Ministry of Industry and Trade of the Czech Republic in the DKRV01 program dedicated to the development of research organizations.

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